

Yoda

research data management

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UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

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Guidance for data package curation in Yoda@WUR v01

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https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/checklist_YODA_V5p.pdf

Curation guidelines for data packages in Yoda@WUR

- ❖ This document describes attention points for curation of data packages for archiving in and publishing from Yoda@WUR. However, at WUR it is currently not possible to publish through Yoda@WUR, but will be possible in the future.
- ❖ Here, a data package refers to a set of files containing data, scripts, and / or source code along with appropriate documentation, that may be structured in various folders.
- ❖ The main goal of curation is to increase FAIRness of a data package using general research data management (RDM) principles and practices.
- ❖ The Yoda data manager is tasked with evaluating the quality and approval / rejection of submissions for archiving to the Yoda vault and submissions for publication from the Yoda vault. The Yoda@WUR data manager only evaluates and advises to improve the data package (incl. file and folder structure, and documentation) submitted in Yoda@WUR. For more info, see [Yoda data manager responsibility](#) on the Utrecht University Yoda website.
- ❖ The researcher(s) (i.e. submitter(s)) remain(s) responsible for adherence to data package quality conditions, contractual obligations, policies, and RDM principles.
- ❖ Please contact data@wur.nl for questions or curation support / advice by data librarians at the WUR Library.

1 Yoda research area vs. Yoda vault

An important part of the Yoda platform is the distinction between the research area and the vault area.

- **The Yoda research area** is the place where users can adjust files (upload, modify, delete, etc.) and is therefore a dynamic area.
- **The Yoda vault** is the place where files are archived and cannot be modified or deleted by a user / submitter. It remains as a secure copy of that file as it was at that point in time and, therefore, is a more static area. Files in the vault are protected against unwanted / accidental modification.

Submitting to the vault is an important step to archive and secure a data package and is a required step if a data package is to be published. Currently, publication is not yet possible at WUR. Further, the intent for submission to the vault (secure raw data and / or intermediate data packages, long-term preservation of data packages) can influence how elaborate an evaluation by the Yoda@WUR data manager needs to be. For example, long term preservation requires a more elaborate evaluation. However, independent of how elaborate the evaluation is, one needs to determine beforehand what characteristics are required in the metadata so that it becomes more easily searchable and findable.

2 Attention points for archiving in the Yoda@WUR vault

Which attention points to use for archiving data packages in the Yoda@WUR vault is up to the Yoda@WUR data manager's discretion. For long-term preservation it is advised to check all. Further, the Yoda@WUR data manager needs to communicate to the researcher whether a submission is accepted or rejected. If rejected, the reasons are included and pointers to improve the data package are given using, for example, the 'yoda_curation_table' Excel or csv file.

2.1 Rightsholder.

Are the rights- and stakeholders defined including special regulations (for example an external funder holds the rights)?

- When applicable, special regulations may indicate whether the data package is allowed to be deposited in this storage platform.
- Any other regulations about the data package should be available in either the Yoda metadata form field 'description', within a readme file and / or a licence file within the data package.

2.2 Creator(s) and contributor(s).

Is the submitter to the vault (one of) the creator(s) of the data package and allowed to deposit the data package?

- If the submitter is not the creator of the data package, the creators need to be included in communication as they are likely holding end-responsibility of the correct provisioning of information about the data package.
- Yoda metadata fields to fill in: 'funder', 'award number', 'creator(s)' and 'affiliation', 'contributor(s)' and 'affiliation(s)'. Preferably, persistent identifiers are used for the affiliations and any creator or contributor entries.
- When in doubt, personal conformation with the research / project group should be attained to ensure that the data package can be deposited.

2.3 Reused materials.

Does the data package describe reused elements from pre-existing materials?

- The Yoda metadata field 'description' should / must clearly indicate whether reused materials are present or referred to.

- If the reused material was already published, then adding those reused materials in the data package is not required.
- The Yoda metadata fields under 'related resource' are filled in ('relation type', 'title', 'persistent identifier').
- Documentation should clearly indicate how the reused materials were attained, processed, and included in the current data package. Preferably scripts are used to attain better reusability of the data processing steps undertaken.

2.4 Sensitive information.

Is there sensitive information present in the data package (personal data, ethical data, business / company data, information to sensitive IT resources, etc.)?

- When applicable, it is strongly recommended to keep personal / company / sensitive IT identifiers separated from pseudonymised or otherwise non-sensitive information. The data package can then more securely be (internally) shared with others without exposing sensitive information.
- When applicable, sensitive information should preferably be submitted separately (e.g. in a separate folder) to the vault.

2.5 Contact address.

Is there a contact address available that can reliably be contacted for decades to come?

- In the readme file, a contact email address is present to which future questions about e.g. data sharing, transfer, publishing, or deletion can be addressed.
- A sustainable email address managed by multiple people (for example a functional email address of a secretariat or the data steward group) is required.

2.6 Retention period.

Is the retention period aligned with the type of information and / or agreements within the project?

- In the Yoda metadata form the field 'retention period' is filled in.
- If the data package includes personal data, then the informed consents should state the retention period of the data package and should take into account the GDPR principles (data minimisation, storage limitation, and accuracy).

- If the data package includes consortium or e.g., company data, the project agreements should state the retention period of the data package.
- The Yoda@WUR data manager is not expected to read all the agreements but can request conformation from the submitter.

2.7 Expiration retention period.

Is there information present on what should be done after expiration of the retention period?

- Within the Yoda metadata form at the field 'retention information' and / or readme file, information should be present on what should be done with the data package after expiration of the retention period.
- Possible responses could be (but are not limited to): 'please contact ...[email address]... to discuss retention of this data package' (see the Contact address section) or 'the data package can be deleted after expiration of the retention period' or 'the data package can be transferred to tape storage after the retention period'.

2.8 Readme file.

Does the data package include a readme file (.txt or .pdf format)?

- It is advised that at least the components of the WUR readme template are used <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7701727>.
- Depending on the discipline and the nature of the data package, the following aspects in the readme file of the data package might be important for contextualisation:
 - o The setup of the research project.
 - o Experimental set-up, when applicable.
 - o The variables.
 - o Documentation of self-defined abbreviations.
 - o For tabular data, headers should be defined in the documentation.
 - o The units of measurement.
 - o The instruments.
 - o Software required to open the files, including version and dependencies.
 - o Sample size.
 - o When scripts are not used to process data, elaborate documentation is required on what processing steps were performed.

- Folder structure documentation of which files can be found where.
- Explanations of what scripts and code do (elaborate comments should be used in scripts).
- Documentation of all file formats present.

2.9 Yoda metadata form.

Is the Yoda metadata form accompanying the data package filled in correctly and completely?

- When the vault submission is intended as long-term preservation, the Yoda metadata form should be filled in as complete as possible / applicable.
- Persistent identifiers for creators and contributors of the data package are advised to be used (such as ORCID).
- Within the Yoda metadata form the field 'key words' holds one word or associated words. New key words (or associated key words) should be provided in a new field (using the 'plus' icon).

2.10 Missing files and folders.

Are the folders described in the documentation present in the data package and vice versa?

- Files that could be related to the experimental set-up documentation should also be present in the data package. When applicable, suggest to add missing elements.

2.11 Formats used.

Are there non-preferred formats being used?

- Check within Yoda@WUR by clicking on the buttons 'actions' --> 'check for compliancy with policy' --> 'DANS Preferred Formats'.
- Check whether non-preferred formats could be converted to preferred formats (for example csv instead of xlsx; for more information see the [DANS preferred formats list](#)). Suggest to the submitter to perform those conversions.
- If non-preferred formats do not have an easy conversion available and the submitter indicates that a preferred format is not available or is not inclined to make changes, make sure to advise the submitter to document all processing

and analysis steps undertaken and the software details (see the readme file section).

2.12 Folder and filenames.

Are folder and filenames consistent, explanatory, and logical?

- Folder and file naming conventions should be consistently applied. For example, when a convention is chosen 'subject_sub-subject_date_version', this convention should be applied as consistently as possible which means that other conventions such as 'date_subject_version' should not be present (unless valid reasons dictate why they should be).
- File and folder names should be as independent as possible from its location. A file in folder 'A' called 'results.csv' and in folder 'B' also called 'results.csv' are not independent of the location nor are they sufficiently descriptive of its contents.
- Folder and filenames should be concise and descriptive (abbreviations are allowed as long as they are documented).
- Special characters such as !@#\$%^&*()``"?'><][should not be used. Use dashes and underscores for white spaces or periods. Lower capitals are recommended where possible.
- Filenames apply consistent versioning where applicable.
- For more information of folder and file naming, see [organising files and folders](#) on the WUR RDM website and this [Wikipedia page](#).

2.13 Folder structure.

Are folder structures consistent and logical?

- A folder structure should separate different subjects / contents appropriately. For example, interview questionnaires should not be in the same folder as laboratory results.
- Raw data should be in its own separate folder and not be placed in, for example, the same folder as processing scripts or processed data.
- A folder structure should not be made too deep making navigating folders tedious. Generally, a folder depth of more than 5 levels should be avoided (unless valid reasons dictate otherwise). A folder structure should not be too shallow as it does not allow proper distinction between contents of files.

2.14 Software required.

- All required software to open files should be clearly documented. This includes the software name, version, where the software is available, and date used.
- Dependencies within software should be clearly documented where appropriate. For example, when R scripts exist that use different R libraries, the names of those libraries and their versions should be documented (similarly for Python and Python packages used).

2.15 Hidden or temporary files

Are there any files created by programs or operating systems that should not be part of the data package?

- Temporary files (.temp, .tmp, files starting with ~\$) should not be required.
- Desktop.ini files are not required.
- Indexing files are often not required (Apple ._, DS_Store, etc).
- History files are often not required and may contain sensitive information of input given in scripts (for example, .Rhistory may show passwords typed if not interactively provided).

2.16 Readability.

Can files be opened correctly?

- When few files are present, it is good practice to determine if the files can all be opened correctly.
- When many files exist, a random selection of a few files can be opened to see if there are file validity issues. The Yoda@WUR data manager is not expected to open dozens to hundreds of files.
- Files and folders are not duplicated.

2.17 Common practices.

Are common data practices adhered to in terms of data representation?

- Files should as much as possible be presented in open formats.
- Some examples to consider when dealing with general tabular data:
 - o Data should be provided in csv or txt files.
 - o Only 1 header row.
 - o Missing values are signified by empty cells.

- Should be comma separated, semi-colon separated, or tab separated (and documented).
- Should avoid mixing of numerals and text between rows of the same columns.
- Should apply consistent usage of labels (for example not use 'male' and 'female' in one column, and 'm' and 'f' in another).
- Some extreme data values in a column may indicate an error (not necessarily so).

3 Attention points for publishing from the Yoda@WUR vault

The publication module of Yoda@WUR is not active as of yet. This chapter is to be used once the publication module of Yoda@WUR is active.

Only a data package already in the vault can be submitted for publication. A data package intended for publication should already have been evaluated with the checklist in the previous chapter followed by additional focus on the points below. However, the end-responsibility of a publication lies with the submitter.

Please note that a publication can be visible to anyone and may have positive (very well structured and documented data package) or negative (poorly structured and documented data package) reputational effects for individuals, research groups, and WUR.

A data package submitter determines what access level the publication receives after approval by the Yoda data manager when filling in the Yoda metadata field 'data package access':

- Open – freely retrievable.

The Yoda metadata form receives a DOI and is publicly available. Within the published metadata form there will be a button 'view contents' which will lead to the associated research data package and can be freely accessed.

- Restricted – available upon request.

After approval of the publication, the Yoda metadata form will receive a DOI and be publicly available. There will be no button 'view contents' available in the published Yoda metadata form. A label will be present stating "Accessibility: Restricted - available upon request". Anyone wanting to get access to the data package will have to do so by contacting the creator of the data package or the contact address provided in the metadata. Note that restricted access can be quite difficult. It requires amongst others:

- o a consistent / sustainable contact address.
- o people available, for the long term, that can evaluate a data package access request. Approval of a request should take into account what the reason is for the request, if the reason is good enough to get insight in people's privacy/sensitive information, does the request weigh up against possible discomfort experienced by subjects or any negative consequences that could result from granting access to the

- o data package, is granting access conform to any contracts / agreements / informed consents, etc.
- o people that send a data sharing agreement when a request has been approved.
- o people that can arrange access to the data package.
- Closed access.

After approval of the publication, only the Yoda metadata form will receive a DOI and be publicly available. A label will be present stating "Accessibility: closed". A 'closed' publication means that access to the data package associated with the metadata cannot be accessed or requested.

3.1 Sensitive information

Is there any type of sensitive information present?

- Sensitive information includes any signatures (for example on informed consents), pictures or videos with identifiable information (for example faces, addresses, unique characteristics, etc), names, addresses, IP addresses, bank accounts, confidential company information, confidential IT infrastructure insights, etc. For more information, see the [sharing guidelines](#) on the WUR RDM website.
- Sensitive information can likely not be published open access. Check the Yoda metadata form field 'Data package access' which should be set to restricted or closed access when sensitive information cannot be uncoupled from non-sensitive information and for which there are no agreements to publish openly.
- If sensitive information is present by accident while everything else contains non-sensitive information, ask the submitter to remove the sensitive information and deposit as a separate vault submission not to be published.

3.2 Licence

Is there a licence chosen fitting the level of access?

- If a user chose 'Open access', then the user can choose between various default licences available. The default CC BY options in the Yoda metadata form usually suffice. If they don't suffice, the license field should be set to 'custom' and a 'licence.txt' needs to be created and placed in the data package parent folder stating the terms of use.

- If a user chose 'Restricted Access' or 'Closed Access', the user can only choose 'custom' licence and will have to place a 'licence.txt' file within the parent folder of the data package to be published. A 'license.txt' can be a copy of an existing licence, the terms of a data sharing agreement, or a simple line stating "access to this data package can only be granted by ..[person or group].. after approval of the request" or "the data package cannot be shared under any circumstances, only employees of the group ...[groupname].. may have access to the data package".

3.3 Contractual obligations

Are there any contractual obligations, agreements, or confidentiality issues?

- The submitter must clearly indicate to the Yoda@WUR data manager and in the documentation that there are no contractual obligations, agreements, or confidentiality issues limiting open access publication. The Yoda@WUR data manager is not expected to read all contracts and agreements, responsibility lies with the submitter of the data package.

3.4 Reused materials

Does the data package describe reused elements from pre-existing materials?

- If the reused materials were not previously published, the submitter must ensure that they are allowed to publish the materials with the current submission.
- If reused materials were published or made available online before, but are required to be published with the current submission, the submitter must ensure that they adhere to the licence(s) / terms of use on the reused materials.

3.5 Creator(s).

Is the submitter (one of) the creator(s) of the data package and allowed to deposit the data package? See also 2.2.

- This point is especially important when a data package will be published, which can impact reputation of all creators and contributors listed as it will be openly visible.

3.6 Value creation

Is there a Data & Software Disclosure Form (DSDF) present?

- The submitter should have confirmation from the head of the chair group or business unit to allow publication (there could be financial reasons not to publish openly).
- When a data package with potential commercial or utilisation value is created, it should be disclosed by completing a [Data & Software Disclosure Form \(DSDF\)](#) (source: [WUR guidelines on Value Creation with Software and Data](#), support at).
- When there is no DSDF present, there is either no added value creation or the submitter is unaware. Consider making the submitter aware.